

HYPERVELOCITY IMPACT OF SPACE DEBRIS ON MULTIPLE COMPOSITE BUMPER: EXPERIMENTS & SIMULATIONS USING LS-DYNA

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Abstract

This paper describes the superiority of carbon/epoxy double bumpers with standoff distance incorporation over single bumpers, which can be used for the spacecraft shielding as a shift towards flexible shielding system. In this research, initially carbon/epoxy CU125NS prepreg was used to manufacture with having stacking sequence of $[(0/\pm 45/90)_2]_s$ in 16 layers, due to their superiority over other commercially available prepreps. Afterwards the specimens were exposed to low Earth orbit environment, where they were attacked with UV, AO, thermal cycling and high vacuum conditions. The last factor of space debris impact was tested by using light gas gun with the Al2017-T4 projectile having mass of 0.25 g within the velocity range of 1500 ± 500 m/s. The total mass loss of 0.42% was found on average for the composites when exposed to LEO environment. It was also being found that the double bumpers in combination of normal and oblique configurations can effectively encounter the space debris impacts in comparison to single bumpers either in normal or oblique configuration. Because the oblique impact events represent 80~90% of actual space debris impacts which a spacecraft experiences during its lifespan. The specific energy absorption for double bumper in normal and oblique configurations with 100 mm standoff distance was found on average 14%, 35% and 50% higher in comparison to that of single bumpers at 45° , 30° and 0° respectively.

In the end LS-DYNA analyses were also done by using SPH module for the double bumpers. The average energy difference of 15~22% was found while comparing with the experimental results. The simulated results helped to understand the space debris impact event and its propagation in a quite effective way.

1. Introduction

The hypervelocity impact of space debris in the low Earth orbit (LEO) region is a serious concern for the spacecraft structural engineers. The increasing population of space debris and their impacts make the things even more worst. According to NASA studies, only 6% of the population in LEO is operational spacecraft while rest of them lies in the category of space junk. More than 21,000 orbital debris are larger than 10 cm known to exist while there are approximately 500,000 particles having a

size in between 1 and 10 cm in diameter. The number of particles smaller than 1 cm exceeds 100 million [1, 2]. The solution to big junks is done by maneuvering the spacecraft, but for the rest spacecraft has to be shielded effectively and intelligently by using advanced and optimized materials. Advance composites materials is one of the promising candidate for this application. But for any material to be used and validated for such application, one has to be aware of the environmental factors which can affect the performance of such systems. The LEO environment

have the following major factors which can affect the system, namely; high vacuum, Atomic Oxygen (AO), Ultraviolet (UV) radiations, thermal cycling and space debris attack.

The vacuum ranges from 10^{-5} ~ 10^{-6} Torr causing the out-gassing especially for composite materials, resulting in the degradation of the composites properties. The AO attack is on average 10^{14} ~ 10^{15} atoms/cm²s on the ram side of the spacecraft resulting in the alteration of material properties. Thirdly, UV radiation usually has wavelengths in the 100~400 nm, with the enough energy to break molecular bonds in polymers such as C-C, C-O, and functional groups, built volatile fragments and alter their material properties. The synergistic effects of AO and UV are more devastating for the materials used for space applications [3]. The other factors include, thermal cycling, where during one day, a spacecraft in LEO completes 14~15 cycles around Earth by encountering the shadow and sun-facing conditions with an average thermal gradient of 150°C. Last parameter is the space debris attack on shielding system of spacecraft in the velocity range of 7~20 Km/s. Majority (80~90%) space debris attack are oblique in nature resulting in ricochet, in-line and normal debris clouds especially in case of metal alloys [4].

Different shielding in form of single or multiple metallic bumpers already had been investigated. Most widely used concept was of Whipple shield and the involvement of Kevlar and Nextel in between the bumper to encounter space debris attack. For multiple bumpers with different materials some components used for shocking projectile while others used for slowing down which make them different in mechanism from that of single bumper [5]. These shielding systems showed their dominance over single bumpers but with the advancement of composite industry, composite materials become superior. The usage of composite materials over metallic alloys in structural applications if justifiable being having high strength and stiffness over conventional alloys and having –ve coefficient of thermal expansion, which is helpful when sun-facing and shadowing effects being considered. Secondly in case of composites, the

fracture mechanics of composite materials including fibre breakage, matrix cracks, etc. were found to be the same for low and hypervelocity impact events [6].

LS-DYNA software is general purpose finite element software used for non-linear structural dynamics and other analysis. In LS-DYNA, dedicated SPH (Smooth particle hydrodynamics) is used for the simulation of space debris impact on composite materials. The beauty of SPH is, it's truly grid free and no computational efforts are required for mesh maintenance in comparison to conventional FE codes [7].

This paper deals with the hypervelocity impact of space debris in the low Earth orbit environment on the composite structures especially when the angle of impact is oblique and multiple bumpers being used in different orientations with predefined standoff distance to check the effect on space debris propagations and carbon/epoxy composites effectiveness. After the experimentation the simulation was conducted by using LS-DYNA with its special SPH module to find out the correlation among experimental and simulated results.

2. Methods and Procedure

During the experimentations, CU125NS was selected for the experimentation on the basis of its experimental superiority over other prepreg in the velocity range of 1000 ± 50 m/s which are available in local market [8]. The CU125NS was prepared by hot melting process at Hankuk Fibres Glass Corporation (South Korea). The stacking sequence of $[(0/\pm 45/90)_2]_s$ in 16 layers was adopted, as the ply thickness and its sequence plays a great role against impact events and material energy absorption characteristics [9, 10]. After stacking the layers in quasi-isotropic sequence, specimens were placed in the autoclave.

By adopting the standard procedures, in the autoclave, specimens were prepared in the dimension range of average 120×120 mm². The average weight was found 36.50g with the average thickness of 1.75 mm.

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Afterwards the specimen were exposed to LEO environment where they were exposed to high vacuum of 10^{-6} to 10^{-7} Torr with the help of rotary and high vacuum diffusion pumps. At the same time, the specimen was exposed to UV radiation with wavelengths in the range of 100~200 nm. Thirdly, atomic Oxygen system used to generate AO flux through weakly ionized remote Oxygen plasma with a radio frequency (RF) plasma source. At the same time, thermal cycling was provided with a Halogen lamp located inside the chamber for heating and copper plate attached to a refrigerator for cooling conditions, simulating the sun facing and shadow scenarios while the spacecraft is in LEO regions. Heating was done radiatively while cooling was provided with conductive link by maintaining the temperature in the range of 100°C to -70°C during experimentation [3]. Only 14 thermal cycles were performed because most of the failures, if occurred due to thermal cycling, usually happened in the first few cycles [11]. The facility where above four parameters were simulated is shown in figure 1. The last and important parameter of the space debris impact was achieved by using light gas gun with Helium and Air at the pressure of 6 bars and 150~250 bars respectively within the velocity range of 1500±500 m/s as shown in figure 2. Inside the light gas gun the obliquity of one bumper was adopted along with normal bumper, as obliquity being proved to be superior than that of normal impact cases [8]. The space debris used was Al2017-T4 having 0.25 g in weight with 5.56 mm in diameter.

The velocity before and after the impact on specimens were measured by laser and magnetic intervalometer. With this velocity the energy absorbed by the composite specimens were calculated.

$$E_{\text{absr}} = \frac{1}{2} m (V_{\text{initial}}^2 - V_{\text{residual}}^2) \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

3. Experimental results

Firstly, CU125NS specimens were exposed to low Earth orbit environment in simulation

chamber, where on average 0.42% total mass loss (TML) was being found in the specimens.

Afterwards, initial experiments were conducted for single bumpers and then followed by double bumpers in different combinations as shown in the figure 3. The configurations used were FN-RI and FI-RN, where F, R, N and I are front, rear, normal and inclined respectively. For these configurations the space debris were initialized with the help of two stage light gas gun. Different impact events were noted for different configurations.

The velocity before and after the impact on specimens were measured and then converted into energy. Afterwards, the energy absorbed by specimens was calculated by the difference of energy before and after the impact.

The figure 4 showed the specific energy absorbed by the single bumper in normal (0°) and oblique (30° and 45°) configurations. For the normal impact, the average specific energy absorption was found 150 J/(g/cm²). While for the oblique impacts of 30° and 45°, it was 220 and 300 J/(g/cm²) respectively within the velocity range of 1000±50m/s.

For the double bumper combination of front and rear in configurations of normal and incline, the energy absorbed by the specimens is shown in figure 5. The average specific energy absorbed by the double bumpers in FN-RI and FI-RN configurations with 100 mm standoff distance was found the same, which was on average 350 J/(g/cm²). The inclined bumpers with no standoff absorbed more specific energy on average.

4. LS-DYNA

LS-DYNA is general purpose finite element software used for non-linear structural dynamics and other analysis. LS-DYNA can handle different types of problems including hypervelocity impacts. Due to the involvement of large mesh deformation during impact modeling, the conventional FE solutions couldn't provide the better solution. For such applications Smooth Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) module is available which can handle large mesh deformation. SPH is based on lagrangian particle

method initially introduced by Lucy and Gingold and Monaghan in 1977 for astrophysical and shock physics problems. The advantage of SPH is being grid free and no computational efforts are required for mesh maintenance. Some limitations like tensile instability can make solution and having difficulty in matching the accuracy of finite difference methods unless an adequate numbers of particles used [12]. In LS-DYNA, spacecraft composite bumpers and projectile both were made with SPH particles. The composite specimens were made by using materials card_059MAT_COMPOSITE_FAILURE_SPH_M ODEL with section SECTION_SPH in SPH module. The AL2017-T4 space debris was made with MAT_ELASTIC_PLASTIC_HYDRO having SECTION_SPH as well. CU125NS properties used during the simulation are available in table 1 [13]. Gruneisen equation of state (EOS) was used for incorporating the high strain rates for Al2017-T4 from data available at Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory reports [14]. For the composites, the limitation was there, MAT card 59 for composites doesn't support EOS, so the strain rate wasn't included for the composites in the analysis, showing limitation of results. The contact definition between SPH spacecraft wall were done in different combinations representing and duplicating the experimental configurations. By using single bumper specimens, followed by multiple bumpers in different combinations with different obliquities. Figure 6 showed the basic modeling of SPH bumpers in normal and oblique configurations and the definition of standoff distance. Total numbers of SPH elements used were 69133 out of which 1533 SPH elements were used for the projectile. The figures 7 and 8 show the space debris propagation for one of the experiment which was done on double bumper at the velocity of 1554.70m/s. The space debris took around 90 μ Sec to impact the second bumper at the standoff distance of 100 mm while doing penetration. The energy absorbed was calculated by post processing the simulation in LS-Prepost. Energy absorption difference was found 16.75% for the velocity of 1554.70 m/s. While comparing the energy absorption from experimental data the simulation

results varied in the range of 15~22%. This was found due to many reasons. Firstly, carbon/epoxy modeling was done in laminate format not layer by layer. Secondly, in SPH modeling, SPH particle sensitivity effect the solution, more number of particles doesn't mean the more accuracy. Sometimes it's the other way around.

5. Discussions

The experimental results concluded that the specific energy absorption pattern for double bumper with standoff distance was much superior then the single bumpers in any of the orientations. The average specific energy absorbed for double bumpers in FN-RI or FI-RN orientations with 100 mm standoff was found 14%, 35% and 50% higher in comparison to that of single bumpers at 45°, 30° and 0° respectively. But when compared with the double bumpers at oblique angles with no standoff distance, the energy absorption was found less. But this orientation of bumpers was found not suitable to actual space debris impact events happening on spacecraft in LEO environment. This case can increase the effectiveness only to specific angle event, but not for all types of oblique events. Although the average energy absorbed by FN-RI and FI-RN systems was found the same, but the damage area found different in both configurations. When the front bumper was inclined, less destruction was found in the second bumper as much of the energy is already been absorbed and projectile already been deformed. All this showed the first bumper obliquity superiority over the first normal bumper.

The damage mechanism was found totally different than that of in metallic alloys. In case of carbon/epoxy composites, the damage and the energy absorption was mostly done by fiber breakage and their deformation and matrix fracture. The breakages of first bumper always result in the much release of epoxy in powder form, which can contaminate the nearby systems. It was observed visually that during impact event epoxy release was high enough to contaminate the system and its

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surroundings easily. That's why, the carbon/epoxy is not recommendable to use at such locations where nearby optics are involved. During exposure to LEO environment, the total mass loss of 0.42% is high enough to disturb the pointing accuracy, if carbon/epoxy system is going to use for optical payloads.

Another interesting observation found was, with the increase of velocity the energy absorption kept on increasing, which is due to the strain rate effects. This effect demonstrates the fluid like behavior of solid at high level of stress in a localized area which usually crossed millions of pound per square inch.

The LS-DYNA used for comparing the experimental results by using SPH module effectively demonstrates the capability of SPH for handling lager mesh deformation. The SPH modeling in the paper for the double bumpers done effectively and energy absorbed by the specimens were compared. The difference was found within the range of 15~22%. This is because of the limitation of SPH module for handling the strain rate effect for composites, but for Al2017-T4 projectile it's been incorporated successfully. The modeled double bumpers although initiated and tested for the velocities obtained during experiments but this system was also found applicable for higher velocities too.

6. Conclusions

In this paper, the experimental and numerical evaluation of carbon/epoxy double bumpers was conducted. It was being found that double bumpers in normal and oblique configurations can effectively encounter the real time space debris impacts in all scenarios. The specific energy absorption for double bumpers was found on average 14%, 35% and 50% higher in comparison to that of single bumpers at 45°, 30° and 0° respectively. While comparing with the double with no standoff distance, energy absorption was found more, but this limit the applicability of results in real time impacts and usage of standoff distance. Lastly the LS-DYNA

results helped to understand the impact event properly along with comparing with experimental results. The difference of 15~22% was found on average, being no inclusion of strain rate effects for composites as LS-DYNA don't support EOS for SPH composites.

7. References

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Fig.1: The low Earth orbit chamber used for experimentations.

Fig.2: The light gas gun.

Fig.3: The configuration inside the light gas gun.

Fig.4: The specific energy absorbed by single bumpers.

Fig.6: LS-DYNA SPH modeling for space debris impact on composites.

Fig.5: The specific energy absorbed by double bumpers in different orientations.

Fig.7: Space debris propagation upto 13 micro-sec.

Fig.8: Space debris penetration into second bumper.

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Fig.9: Post processed results for the composites (FN-RI).

Fig.10: Post processed results for the composites (FI-RN).

Table 1: The properties of CU125NS Carbon/epoxy prepreg [13]

E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	E_3 (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	G_{13} (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	V_{12}
130	10	10	4.85	4.85	3.62	0.31
V_{12}	V_{12}	X_T (MPa)	X_C (MPa)	Y_T (MPa)	Y_C (MPa)	S (MPa)
0.31	0.52	1933	1051	51	141	61